

DIVIDEND POLICY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES OF EU COUNTRIES

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The price at which a firm may be sold in the market with unrestricted competition is commonly regarded as its market value. These concerns pertain more to JSC. The primary source of income for the capital owners now comes from the growth in the value of the company's assets. The primary goal of investors is to raise the share price on the market. The goal of maximizing a company's stock value is predicated on the idea that raising the market price of the stock, rather than the dividend income, is what increases the wealth of the company's owners. As a result, there has always been a need and interest in developing more useful methods for determining the market worth of the firm and its management as well as for managing the procedures involved in raising that value. Thus, management theory first introduced the idea of firm value management.

The subject of creating successful dividend policies in market economies has been the focus of several scientific investigations. The process of developing a company's dividend policy is taken into account in theoretical methods based on how it will affect the company's market value and the well-being of its shareholders.

Large dividend-paying firms are valued by the market. The "bird in the hand" argument, which highlights the significance of dividend policy, is predicated on the idea that there is a dividend policy in place that establishes the objective (ideal) level of payouts [1].

One of the top ten pressing issues unresolved by economic theory is the distribution of profits and dividend policy. This problem is still up for discussion among scientists and practitioners today [2].

An investor's primary goal is to reduce or eliminate financial risk; dividend payments are preferable to deferring income till later in life. Furthermore, dividend payments help investors feel less apprehensive about the viability and profitability of making an investment in the business [3].

Economist J. Ataniyazov have studied the importance of stock market instruments as alternative resource sources in strengthening the resource bases of commercial banks [4].

E. Alimardonov conducted the study pertaining to the growth of JSC's activity scope and resource bases, as well as the establishment of worldwide financial centers and their acknowledgment on a global scale [5].

In the literature on economics, many definitions of dividends and dividend policy have been developed. It should be emphasized that the most often used definitions of these ideas are as follows: A method of making money and giving it to shareholders is dividend policy. One way to conceptualize dividend policy is as a component of financial strategy that aims to maximize shareholder wealth through the efficient distribution of earnings [6]. A dividend is a sort of income that joint stock businesses provide its shareholders in exchange for a specific portion of their net earnings. Nearly all businesses file financial reports to tax authorities and condense their annual financial results during the first quarter.

In the first and second quarters of the year after the reporting year, the question of paying dividends is discussed and decided upon in the general meeting of founders or shareholders.

The procedure of distributing net profit is the first step in the system that determines the value of dividends in joint stock enterprises. The board of directors adopts the decision about net profit distribution, which is then authorized by the general board of shareholders. Funds allotted for the development of a reserve fund, acquisition of new machinery and technologies, activities expansion, manufacturing process expansion, and share dividend payments are included in the distribution of net profit.

Joint stock firms make choices on dividend payments based on the dividend policy that has been authorized by the company. Dividend amounts vary depending on the kind of shares. Ordinary share dividends fluctuate based on the amount of earnings and how it is divided among shareholders. Conversely, with a preferred share, the dividends are fixed and unaffected by the level of earnings. As a result, one of the key responsibilities of the finance management is helping joint-stock firms create and implement an efficient dividend policy, which calls for a thorough grasp of the variables influencing it.

The most crucial company action that gains investor trust is paying dividends. Businesses are intricate systems that depend on ongoing collaboration with banks, tax authorities, shareholders, and other institutions to guarantee society's net profit. The significance of the registrar (depository), which takes on the roles of the agency for the issuer's dividend payment and scrupulously adheres to the legal process, must be emphasized.

The dividend policy sets forth the process and requirements for obtaining dividends, and the JSC general meeting approves the total amount of dividends. The location and significance of the organization's operations, as well as the focus of business and financial management, are all mentioned in this context by the dividend policy.

Each joint stock company's dividend policy formation is unique, but all of them go through the same general stages: selecting the dividend policy type in line with the developed development strategy; deciding on the terms and formats of dividend payments; and assessing the dividend policy's effectiveness.

Important considerations about dividend policy include whether or not a company's market value is impacted by its dividend payments and how the market assesses businesses that distribute substantial dividends to their shareholders.

The issue of determining tax rates in respect to the income obtained by investors in joint stock firms' securities is approached differently in various nations. For instance, the income tax rates on dividends are different in Germany, Japan, and France; the tax rates on dividends and reinvested income are the same in the UK, Australia, and Canada. Since different taxpayer categories sometimes pay varying tax rates in many nations, joint-stock corporations frequently customize their dividend policies to appeal to particular investor groups.

Current research on the dividend policies of different firms reveals that shares of businesses that consistently distribute dividends to their owners have been gaining value recently. However, compared to smaller and more scattered owners, institutional investors are more equipped and willing to keep an eye on corporate governance. Corporate dividend policy can therefore be crafted to draw in institutional investors, who can then offer monitoring services.

There isn't a definite stance on the dividend policy now. A dividend policy is characterized as a feature of a joint stock company's profitable operations and a sign of the stability of the corporate management structure. In a contemporary business, the dividend income per share is just one measure of the success of the dividend policy; another is the thoroughness and adaptability of the established process for determining the dividend amount based on the business's financial status and growth objectives.

The internal papers of the joint-stock firm specify the process for determining, authorizing, and disbursing dividends. This is done to inform interested parties and shareholders about the fundamentals of exercising property rights on both ordinary and preferred shares.

Even with the recent economic upheavals in our nation, the study of dividend policy and the intricacies surrounding its formulation continues to get insufficient attention. Simultaneously, the fundamental tenets of the dividend policy of the nation's top corporations, the profit distribution mechanism, the dividend computation process, and the prerequisites for dividend disbursement have been established.

Simultaneously, a comparative examination of the actions of the top businesses reveals that they adhere to various dividend policies, ranging from the residual principle policy to the policy of sustaining a steady volume or growth of dividends, contingent on the operational circumstances and developmental phases. Businesses in our nation set aside 10-20% of the society's net profit, but commercial banks only set aside a maximum of 5% of their profits for dividend payments. This figure approaches 40% in real-world applications. Investor interest in securities from these nations will thus be comparatively strong.

However, the company's dividend payment is not seen as a means of modifying its market value. The dividend policy's primary objective is to make the firm more appealing to investors by raising dividend payments.

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